

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SELECTION OF SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL RELATIONSHIP CRITERIA

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Abstract: The article discusses the relationship between the individual and society. The socio-psychological significance of the relationship and the specificity of the selection of criteria for the relationship are discussed.

Keywords: Human, social, psychological, social, psychological.

It is known that the relationship, as a subjective phenomenon, is a function of the activity of consciousness in reflecting the external world and in a way that ensures its regulatory function (K.K. Platonov 1982). The system of relationships in a person is manifested through the motive of activity and emotional-volitional qualities aimed at realizing their goal.

The social psychological significance of the relational factor, which serves to ensure the harmony of the individual and society, is such that, on the one hand, it is a subject of activity ("a building constructed, a specific poetic line, a tree planted, a song created or performed", etc.), and on the other hand, it manifests itself as a means with the help of which a person establishes himself in social life. Because this thing was created for other people. Through this, the relationship between people is directly reflected, a relationship in the way of working on a common thing is created that equally concerns those who create and those who perform, as well as those who consume and those who are assimilated, and this relationship cannot but be of great importance for the psychological defense process of the individual, which serves the social development of the individual. Social psychological relationships are a factor that reflects the interconnectedness between people in various social spheres.

In this regard, the directions of "we-we", "we-you" or "me-team", "team-me", "me-team-society" also define certain practical directions for psychological service.

A thorough and in-depth analysis of social psychological relationships from a psychological point of view is of great practical importance.

The social psychological approach to the individual, which is the basis of the attitude criterion, is evaluated by the content of the object. Therefore, in social psychological literature, the individual's attitude to society, his attitude to his social and labor obligations, his attitude to members of society, and his attitude to himself are interpreted on the basis of a certain hierarchical system.

These relationships can clearly reflect a person's lifestyle, orientations, moral ideals, and image. This allows us to speculate about the system of social activity associated with each person's relationships. Observations and scientific analysis show that the process of attitude to educational activity also has its own hierarchical system in the psychological direction of the individual, and on the basis of this system it is possible to study the manifestation, results and dynamics of individual activity. Because, based on a certain hierarchical structure of a particular psychological criterion, it is of great importance to conduct theoretical and scientific reasoning about this criterion. Thus, the relevant attitude criteria, its hierarchical system and aspects of involvement in educational activity are identified. In addition, it should be noted that in studying the attitude criterion, all researchers directly associate it with the parameters that reflect the internal goodwill of the subject towards the object: the content of emotional experience, activity and determination.

The theoretical basis of the criterion for forming an attitude towards oneself is that each person, if he is demanding of himself, can realize all the possibilities that he has of social value and serve to ensure personal activity in this sphere. There are many theories that confirm the social value and importance of the formation of self-esteem, and in all of them, one or another aspect of self-esteem is deeply analyzed and studied as an important factor that contributes to the development of the individual. It can even be noted that self-esteem, as a special defense mechanism, is at the center of advanced general psychodiagnostic literature and research that has been recognized today.

Thus, protecting oneself from “unpleasant” (naturally emotional) events is considered the most important aspect of protecting one's relationship to oneself. In order to avoid exposing oneself to unpleasant emotions, the subject (person) sacrifices certain aspects and experiences related to the processes that are inherent in the image of his true “I”. A person can act on the basis of a certain principle: “Yes, I am not so good, because in some cases I am “empty”, “weak”, but I am not bad.” The preservation and strengthening of the norm of self-esteem serves to ensure the systematic development of the scope of opportunities for external social objective activity and, at the same time, the expression of internal personal activity.

Indeed, the manifestation of an active and positive attitude towards oneself begins first with the desire for self-understanding and self-development. Theoretical and scientific analyses and conclusions on the criteria of attitude to activity, the psychology of activity and its social significance allow us to accept the high level of integration of attitude to activity as an important criterion for the effectiveness of attitude motivation. Because the definition given to activity (i.e.: “Activity is the internal (mental) and external (physical) activity of a person, directed by a conscious goal”) itself expresses a set of human attitudes to one degree or another. Accordingly, three (positive, indifferent, negative) levels of attitude towards activity can be conditionally identified.

a) The manifestation of a positive attitude towards activity, in our opinion, occurs on the basis of the demand for the social content of the activity and satisfaction with the product of the activity.

b) Indifferent (superficial) attitudes towards activity, in our opinion, result from insufficient satisfaction with the requirements and results of activity, lack of stable interests in activity, insufficient provision of harmony between activity and the social development of the individual, and engagement in activity simply out of compulsion.

c) The manifestation of negative attitudes towards activity is characterized by the manifestation of only material-compulsive actions towards activity or an extremely low level of satisfaction with the emotional-social content of the activity and its product, when there is a lack of adequacy between the individual's world of individuality and the demands of activity.

The purpose of dividing the relational system into these types is to provide a more in-depth understanding and explanation of certain social psychological aspects that express social activity in a relational manner, relative to activity.

Conclusion. The above considerations suggest that the manifestation of an active-positive attitude in each person's interpretation can be based on the satisfaction of their needs with the product, while the rest expresses a set of actions that are decided on the basis of satisfaction with the product of activity and the individual's satisfaction with his own activity, as well as the satisfaction of his social needs.

Theoretical and scientific foundations are used in the development and application of special methods aimed at identifying criteria (indicators) that express the manifestation of active-positive attitudes towards activity.

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